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CONVECTIVE MIXING IN GAS MIXTURES CONTAINING GREENHOUSE GASES

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Целью исследования было изучение термодинамических свойств и фазового поведения системы H₂ + R12 - Ar в диапазоне концентраций фреона-12. Экспериментальные исследования проводились при постоянном давлении 0,29 мПа и температуре 298,0 К с использованием смеси водорода (H₂), фреона-12 (R12) и аргона (Ar). Были исследованы концентрации фреона-12 в диапазоне от 0,058 до 0,319 молярных долей, чтобы получить представление о поведении и свойствах системы.

Abstract

The study aimed to explore the thermodynamic properties and phase behavior of the H₂ + R12 - Ar system within a range of freon-12 concentrations. The experimental investigations were conducted at a constant pressure of 0.29 MPa and a temperature of 298.0 K, using a mixture of hydrogen (H₂), freon-12 (R12), and argon (Ar). Freon-12 concentrations ranging from 0.058 to 0.319 molar fractions were examined to gain insights into the system's behavior and properties.

Ключевые слова: диффузия, газ, смеси, КОНВЕКТИВНОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ.

Keywords: diffusion, gas, mixtures, convective stability.

Experiments on the study of multicomponent mixing in gases at elevated pressure [1], diffusion of solution vapors into an inert gas [2] have registered convective flows leading to a synergistic effect associated with a significant increase in the mixing rate of system components and the intensity of mass transfer, as a rule, the heaviest component of the mixture in density. Such a transfer is not typical for diffusion.

The emergence of a priority transfer mode for a component with specified properties is due to a significant difference in the diffusion coefficients of the components. At the same time, the difference in diffusion coefficients creates conditions for a nonlinear distribution of concentrations. With an increase in the content of the component with the highest molecular weight in the system, the nonlinearity of the concentration distribution becomes more pronounced and leads to an inversion of the density gradient. The presence of a minimum (maximum) in the density distribution is the cause of convective instability [3].

The effect of preferential transfer of a certain component of the mixture arising in multicomponent gas (liquid) mixtures is a potentially important mechanism for solving this problem. This effect allows you to increase the concentration of certain components in the

mixture, which makes them more accessible for subsequent purification or collection.

The study of the mechanisms of the influence of the diffusion abilities of greenhouse gases on the intensification of convective mixing in the mode of priority transfer of a component with specified properties is of great practical importance. Understanding this process makes it possible to develop more effective methods of cleaning gases from greenhouse components, which in turn contributes to reducing emissions and improving the environmental situation.

The effect of preferential transfer of a certain component of the mixture arising in multicomponent gas (liquid) mixtures can be used in the purification of natural and associated petroleum gases from components that cause the greenhouse effect. Therefore, the disclosure of the mechanisms of the influence of the diffusion abilities of greenhouse gases on the intensification of convective mixing in the mode of priority transfer of a component with specified properties is an urgent task.

To predict the occurrence of concentration convective flows in vertical channels for isothermal triple gas mixtures, a linear stability analysis was used, applied to the problem of convective stability in a cylindrical circular channel [1].

The studies were carried out with the H₂ + R12 – Ar system in the range of freon-12 concentrations from 0.058 to 0.319 mole fractions at p = 0.29 MPa and T = 298.0 K. The coefficients of mutual diffusion of components under normal conditions have the following values: $D_{\text{H}_2\text{-Ar}} = 0.725 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2/\text{c}$, $D_{\text{H}_2\text{-R12}} = 0.365 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2/\text{c}$, $D_{\text{Ar-R12}} = 0.101 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2/\text{c}$. A cylindrical channel with the following geometric characteristics was used in the calculations: $d = 6,1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}$ and $L = 70,05 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}$. According to the calculation results, distributions of component concentrations and mixture density along the length of the diffusion channel were obtained, as well as a stability map on the plane (Ra1, Ra2) with the mutual arrangement of stability lines and zero density gradient and Rayleigh partial numbers. The analysis of the data obtained indicates that a nonlinear distribution of the R12 concentration is observed in the H₂ + R12 – Ar system, and in the range of freon-12 concentrations

from 0.2 to 0.319 mole fractions, the density profile has a minimum, i.e. in this area a convective mode of priority freon-12 transfer is implemented.

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